

Artificial Intelligence for Neglected Tropical Diseases: Enhancing Diagnosis, Drug Discovery and Public Health Surveillance

Debajit Dutta¹, Monideepa Dey¹, Gyandeeep Bhattacharyya¹, Partha Pratim Saikia¹, Minerva Kalita², Khyati Mishra¹, Juti Rani Devi*¹, Bhargab Jyoti Sahariah¹

¹department of pharmaceuticals, NETES Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Nemcare Group of Institution, Mirza, Kamrup, Assam, India

²department of pharmacology, NETES Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Nemcare Group of Institution, Mirza, Kamrup, Assam, India

ABSTRACT

Neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) continue to affect the high risk populations in low income countries, where diagnosis are delayed, have been limited therapeutics options and poor surveillance systems remain major barriers to control. Artificial Intelligence becomes an emerging and promising tool to address these gaps by improving the detection of diseases, accelerating drug discovery, and helping in drug repurposing and strengthening in outbreak prediction. This review summarizes the recent applications of Machine Learning, Deep Learning and Explainable AI in NTD management, with importance in Leishmaniasis, Schistosomiasis, Chagas Disease and Human African Trypanosomiasis. AI based models shown value in biomarker discovery, microscopic image analysis, clinical symptom interpretation and epidemiological forecasting using multimodal datasets including genomic, imaging, environmental and clinical information. Concurrently, AI has demonstrated potential in target identification, virtual screening, physicochemical property prediction and formulation development as a result reducing its time, cost and experimental burden in drug development. Though its has advantages, major challenges are there which includes data scarcity, model interpretability, external validation and equitable deployment in endemic regions. Overall AI offers a powerful framework for improving diagnosis, therapy discovery and public health surveillance in NTDs. With continuing collaboration with clinicians, data scientists and public health researcher it will be essential to translate these advances into practical and scalable solutions for affected populations.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Neglected Tropical Diseases, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Diagnosis, Drug Discovery, Surveillance.

INTRODUCTION

The neglected tropical diseases are those diseases which are infectious and principally impact the limited commercial incentives. As these diseases have been neglected for the decades, results in limited progress in drug development and diagnosis. Reason behind the overlooking is mainly general disregard for the developing country and recently it's because of the high focus on HIV/AIDs, tuberculosis and malaria (1). According to the study of World Bank, 51% of the sub-Saharan Africa population the major focus for

these diseases lives on less than US\$1.25 per day and 73% lives on less than US\$2 per day (2). The WHO estimated that more than 1.6 billion individuals in 149 nations require treatment or diagnosis strategies for NTDs, which together result in estimated 19 million years of healthy life lost annually (3). These NTDs includes diseases like leishmaniasis, Buruli ulcer, Chagas disease, Leprosy. These conditions often lead to long term disability, financial struggle and social shame (4). The limited research and highly global prevalence make NTDs a scientific challenge that demands innovative approach. Traditional

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

management of various NTDs faces multiple struggles like delayed diagnosis and reliance on laboratory management which contains labor-intensives and required the trained specialists. Diagnosis for leishmaniasis took several weeks for laboratory confirmation (5, 6). In comparison to other diseases the innovations in these fields are very less leads to a huge gap in innovation. Only 13 new drugs are introduced in the period of 1975-1999 for NTDs (7). Similarly only 5 drugs are introduced in the phase during 2000-2011 and those are also new indication

or formulation of existing drug not new chemical moiety for NTDs which remain low even through 2025, illustrating the persistent innovation gap (8). After this period funding for the NTD is notably increases upto US\$3.045 billion in 2011 (9). After this funding new medical products are coming for the NTD. It is also known that drug discovery and development takes a huge cost along with risk of failure. This increases global burden of disease to major tropical infectious diseases.

Table1: Global burden to major tropical infectious diseases (10)

Infection	Global Prevalence (millions)	Population at risk (millions)	Annual mortality (thousands)	Disability adjusted life years (millions)	Region of highest prevalence
Lymphatic filariasis	51	860	<5	2.8	Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, Southeast Asia
Schistosomiasis	240	780	16	3.3	Sub-Saharan Africa
Leishmaniasis	12	350	51	2.1	India, South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America, Caribbean, and Mediterranean region
Human African Trypanosomiasis	0.3	60	48	1.5	Sub-Saharan Africa
Chagas' disease	10	120	15	0.7	Latin American and Caribbean

To overcome all of this AI comes into the action and offers a revolutionary opportunity not only in drug development but also in diagnostic and surveillance. AI techniques, including machine learning, deep learning and image recognition transforms the complex healthcare task to a ease task and extract meaningful data large datasets. Artificial Intelligence is a broad spectrum that focuses on enabling machines to mimic human intelligence, including learning, reasoning, decision making etc (11). Machine Learning and Deep Learning are the core subfield of AI. Machine Learning allows the algorithm to learn from the previous large datasets and keep improving the predictive accuracy without explicit programming (12). Deep Learning is the subset of Machine Learning where DL applies artificial neural networks with multiple layers to process complex and high

dimensional data. DL has achieved to that state that it often surpasses traditional ML methods (11,12). The importance of AI in healthcare particularly in NTD has been increasing for its ability to process and analyze huge datasets from the genomic sequences. AI outperforms traditional methods in managing complex data of healthcare results in the earlier diagnosis and improved decision making (13). AI addresses the high level data complexity using algorithms by processing multimodal data like imaging, genomics to detect early disease signs which aren't noticeable to human analysts or any traditional statistical methods (14). AI model like deep neural networks have demonstrated higher accuracy and faster analysis for cancer detection, sepsis prediction or cardiovascular risk compared to traditional methods. AI also reduces the diagnostic delays,

minimizes unnecessary interventions and also support efficient for health care resources (15). Recent advances in AI and ML have demonstrated high potential in drug discovery for neglected diseases by offering faster, cost effective and highly accurate identification of novel drug molecule (16). AI & ML models speed up the discovery of drugs by screening million of compounds within some days instead of taking months by traditional methods. By screening AI/ML can predict the biological activity and also identify the effectiveness of drug molecule. As a result it will reduce the experimental workload, time of development and costs of research by improving its accuracy and success rates (10). In the same manner, for repurposing AI algorithms identifies new therapeutic candidates from the existing compounds noticing an important strategy as the funding is limited for NTD innovations (8). For diagnosis, DL

algorithm and image-recognition system have greater sensitivity and accuracy than conventional way for detecting parasites and skin lesions associated with leishmaniasis overcoming the reliability on highly trained specialist and also early detection of it (5). AI-based surveillance tools integrating with environmental, climatic and epidemiological data have higher accuracy and timeless in predicting outbreaks pattern and distribution of vector, significantly increasing the early-warning system and public health alertness (1). Therefore, this review aims to explore the present and upcoming application of AI in NTDs as it is positioned to be revolutionized in NTD management by enhancing its diagnostics, drug discovery and surveillance. AI in its potential can improved the health outcomes in underserved populations by continue innovation, ethical oversight and global collaboration.

Figure 1: Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Neglected Tropical Diseases including drug discovery, diagnosis, surveillance and public health decision support

2. Prisma Guidelines

A comprehensive literature search was done to gather relevant published studies on application of Artificial intelligence in Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs), focusing on diagnosis, drug discovery and public health surveillance. Electronic databases like PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect were systematically searched for

articles published between 2013 and 2026. The literature search was performed using combinations of keywords and Boolean operators such as: “Artificial Intelligence”, “Machine learning”, “Neglected Tropical Diseases”, “AI in diagnosis”, “AI in drug discovery”, “AI in health surveillance”, “NTDs and diagnosis AI”, “NTDs and Machine Learning”, “AI and infectious disease”.

Manual screening of reference lists was also performed from selected articles to identify additional relevant studies. Duplicate articles obtained from multiple databases were removed before screening.

The retrieved studies were screened based on title, abstract, and full-text evaluation. Articles were included if they:

- Were published in peer-reviewed journals,
- Were written in English language,
- Focused on AI application, diagnosis, Drug discovery, prediction
- Reported outcomes related to diagnosis, drug discovery, epidemiological modelling

Studies were excluded if they:

- Were duplicate publications,
- Lacked sufficient scientific or methodological rigor
- Consisted only of conference abstracts, editorials, or incomplete reports,
- Studies on unrelated AI applications or NTDs.

The final selection of studies was based on scientific relevance, methodological clarity, data quality, and contribution to advancing the understanding of AI-driven approaches in NTD management. The study selection process was summarized using a PRISMA flow diagram.

Figure2: Schematic Representation of PRISMA flow diagram of Literature Selection Process

3. AI-driven in Drug Discovery & Pharma Application in NTDs

AI is transforming the drug discovery and pharmaceutical development for NTDs by making it faster, cost effective and data driven approaches to overcome the historical innovation gap in this area. NTDs such as Lymphatic filariasis, Schistosomiasis, Leishmaniasis, Human African Trypanosomiasis, Chagas' disease are generally neglected in terms of research funding or incentives especially in low

income countries which results in limited chemical entities and heavily dependence on repurposed drugs (17). For this AI-aided method becomes a powerful tool kit for new chemical entities identification, drug-property prediction, repurposing increasing the pace from hit discovery to dosage forms (16).

3.1 Artificial Intelligence-Facilitated Molecular Target Identification for Optimized Drug Bindings:

Drug-target interaction (DTI) identification and prediction are crucial for modern drug discovery for NTDs where known targets are limited and resources for advance screening are limited. AI- models offers integrate multi modal data which includes genomic sequences, transcriptomic profiles, disease networks and drug-protein interactions to identify the supposed target linked with pathogens causing NTD like *Leishmania spp.*, *Trypanosoma cruzi*, *Schistosoma spp.* These models help to prioritizing enzymes, transporters and signaling proteins which are important for parasitic survival but structurally different from their human homologs, results in expanding the treatment window (18). Many studies have shown that deep learning and graph methods include Transformer based architectures and graph neural networks can predict the drug candidates for NTDs targets. For instance network based analyses have been used to indentify kinase inhibitors or anti metabolic drugs (16). By combining genetic linkage, disease gene associations, DTI data offers information on drug and protein structures, interactions, clinical outcomes, and side effects which highlights off-target and safety liabilities decreasing attrition in later stages of development (19).

3.2 Predictive analysis of drug Properties using artificial-intelligence equipped models:

AI-driven prediction analytics is developing the way how physicochemical and biopharmaceutical properties of NTDs drug are characterized. Deep learning and Machine Learning models are trained with large compounds libraries which can predict solubility, lipophilicity, permeability and also the metabolic stability for novel or repurposed drugs which surpass the traditional QSAR approaches in accuracy and robustness (19). These models are valuable for NTDs where existing drugs which have low solubility, low oral bioavailability or significant toxicity. New AI frameworks combining molecular descriptors, 3D structural features experimental data to predict in vitro performance and in vivo performance which enables the virtual prioritization of lead moiety before synthesis. By cancelling out the high risks compound in initial phase, AI based property predict and supports the selection of drug candidates with favorable developability profiles for NTD programs (20).

3.3 AI as catalyst in drug development

Besides target identification and property prediction, AI is increasing the boarder drug development pipeline for NTDs. From hit to lead and lead optimization to pre-clinical safety evaluation, AI-assisted the workflows to integrate chemical, biological and clinical data to help in decision making under uncertainty. With more resource available, this can be done in shorter timelines, low cost with higher success rates in advancing NTD related candidates (21). AI- driven platforms can combine multi-omics data, pharmacokinetic simulations and toxicity profiles enhance the candidate selection and dosing strategies. Some models are trained on previous clinical trial data for some agents which can suggest optimum dose ranges and regimens that balanced out the efficacy and safety for NTDs that often affect the low and middle income countries and population (22). In this way, AI not only helps in molecular discovery but also reduce the risk of subsequent stages of development, preclinical evaluation to early-phase clinical trials (17).

3.4. Artificial Intelligence Driven Drug Repurposing Approaches

Repurposing of drug is a very attractive strategy especially for NTDs within the limited number of chemical entities and the high cost of de novo drug discovery. AI based repurposing can be broadly divided into target – centric and disease – centric approaches (23). Target centric methods focus on to identify the new ligands for NTD related targets whereas disease centric methods focus on shared biological pathways between different diseases to uncover new indications for existing drugs (20). Some studies have applied network-based and deep learning based models to identify the chemical moiety for NTDs by studying the drug target and disease gene networks. For instance polypharmacology aware models have been used to check the approved drugs for activity against like Kinetoplastid enzymes results in highlighting kinase inhibitors and anti parasitic agents with potential for Chagas diseases or Human African Trypanosomiasis (24). Some other methods includes phenotypic screening-guided ML, integrate cellular response data and transcriptomic signatures to mark the compounds with anti parasitic activity from

large compound libraries (25). These AI driven repurposing offers a rapid, low cost pathway to increase the therapeutic arsenal for NTDs while keeping the safety and pharmacokinetic data that are available for marketed drugs (26).

3.5. Artificial Intelligence-Aided Formulation Development for Enhanced Therapeutic Efficacy in Tropical Diseases

After a known compound is identified, AI is being applied to optimize the formulation for increasing its therapeutic efficacy, stability and patient compliance for the BTDs endemic regions (27). ML and DL can predict the key formulation related properties such as solubility, dissolution rate, and polymorphism stability under different temperature and humidity results in decreasing the extensive trial and error experiments. These models generally combine the molecular descriptors, historical formulation data, in-vitro performance datas to guide the design of suitable dosage forms (28). AI-assisted formulation design is done for particular relevance to NTDs drugs with challenging physicochemical profiles (28). For example, lipid-based and polymeric nanocarriers,

solid dispersions and amorphous systems have been explored to increase the oral bioavailability and tissue targeting for disease like leishmaniasis (29). AI-assisted tools can predict the required excipients composition, drug lipid ratios, process parameters which required for achieving the optimal encapsulation efficiency, particle size and release kinetics (30). By combining the high throughput screening data and *in silico* design of experiments (DoE), AI-driven work can reduce the number of experimental runs by upto several-fold, increasing the pace of the development of stable, patient-friendly formulation suitable for low-resources setting (31). Additionally, AI-facilitated risk assessment helps in early identification of candidates which are vulnerable to poor bioavailability or instability in formulation which enables the team to prioritize only the most promising leads for further development (32). In the context of NTDs, where logistical constraints and cold chain limitations are common, these AI driven formulation can helps in developing strong, temperature stable and easy to administer dosage forms results in increasing the treatment adherence and health outcomes in low income populations (28).

Figure3: AI-assisted drug discovery and development pipeline for neglected tropical diseases.

4. AI in Diagnostics for Tropical Diseases

AI is increasingly being applied to improve the accuracy, speed and scalability of diagnosis for tropical diseases which includes NTDs. In limited resource settings, trained specialists and laboratory

infrastructure are generally scarcity, AI-assisted diagnostic tools can helps in early detection, reducing misdiagnosis and also can guide with therapeutic interventions (33). This section mainly focuses on AI-driven biomarker discovery, microscopic image analysis, clinical symptom modeling and the role of

explainable AI (XAI) in precisely identification of tropical diseases (34).

4.1. Artificial Intelligence adapted aid as a detection of Biomarker for early diagnosis of Tropical Diseases

Biomarkers are molecular biomarkers that drive and reflect disease states. They play a critical role in disease diagnosis, therapeutic target discovery, and drug development in the context of tropical and neglected tropical diseases; reliable biomarkers are especially in demand because of overlapping of clinical presentations and have limited access to definitive diagnostic. AI-powered predictive pipelines have revolutionized biomarker discovery by integrating complicated, high-dimensional datasets which includes genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics and clinical parameters to identify disease-specific signatures (35). However, the area still needs a solid, cross-disciplinary framework that systematically links AI pipelines to disease-specific biological findings. Previous efforts have often on narrow therapeutic domains or isolated stages of biomarker discovery pipelines, leaving a significant void in translational utility (34). A recent review that analyzed 236 AI-driven biomarker discovery researches mapped 147 diseases into 19 different therapeutic domains and systematized trends in data sources, data modalities, preprocessing techniques feature engineering, AI models and explainability

methods. This work gives a structured resource to identify current trends and gaps, it lays the foundation for future developments such as multimodal AI frameworks and multitask learning model tailored to complex biological data in NTDs (36). Especially for tropical infections AI has help to identify the biomarker candidates from regular laboratory and clinical data. For instance, a study involving 40 clinicians managing tropical infections were considered. The most prevalent tropical infections like scrub typhus, leptospirosis, dengue, and malaria were analyzed generally available laboratory parameters such as sodium, total bilirubin, albumin, lymphocytes count and platelets count alongside clinical features that include abdominal discomfort, arthralgia, myalgia, and urine output (37). While multinomial logistic regression yielded has relatively low predictability for scrub typhus (around 38%), while dengue, malaria, and leptospirosis had predictabilities of 60.7%, 62.5%, and 66% respectively using dengue as a reference. While binary classification machine learning techniques demonstrated an average of 79–84% for one vs. other comparisons and 69–88% for one vs. one illness category. In contrast the multiclass machine learning models for simultaneous differentiation among tropical diseases showed an overall accuracy of 55–60% (38). Highlighting both the potential and the current limitations of AI based biomarker-driven diagnosis.

Figure4: AI-enabled diagnostic workflow for neglected tropical diseases from patient sample acquisition to clinical decision support

4.2. Implementation of Artificial Intelligence in Microscopic Image Analysis for Precise Detection

AI/ML transformed the analysis of microscopic images, enabling faster, more consistent and more accurate diagnosis of tropical diseases. In parasitology, AI models can detect the disease parasite on blood smears to identify *Leishmania amastigotes* in tissue imprints or quantify helminth eggs in stool samples, often with performance comparable to or exceeding that of experienced microscopists (39). Similarly for bacteriology and mycology, AI-driven image analysis helps in detection of mycobacteria, fungi from stained slides and histopathological images (16). Apart from this AI enabled systems can analyze chest X-rays, microscope slides, daily laboratory results, and vital signs to predict the sepsis risk by interpreting the chemical notes via processing natural-language and classify the genomic data to detect infections and also the pattern of antimicrobial resistance. When appropriately validated and monitored, these technologies provide faster results, more consistent readings, minimizing unnecessary use of antibiotics and directing care on the critically ill patients (40). For tropical diseases, AI-based image analysis not only improves the diagnosis accurately but also increases the laboratory throughput and supports health-care in low income population where expertise is limited (41).

4.3. Model Based Clinical symptom interpretation for Precise Identification of Tropical Diseases

Soft computing and machine learning approaches have shown considerable value in medical diagnosis and prediction of outcome by identifying the complex patterns in clinical datasets (37). Although many applications mainly focused on imaging-based analysis, ML models are being used to interpret the clinical symptoms and predict the identification of tropical and infectious diseases. These techniques are generally relevant in tropical regions where disease such as malaria, dengue, scrub typhus, leptospirosis and other infections share overlapping clinical presentations making different diagnosis challenging (38). Infectious agents, such as parasitic worms (helminths), viruses, bacteria, and protozoa, can be transmitted to humans via an infected person, a vector

(animal or insect), or environmental vehicle (soil, plants, cloth, etc.) (42). The warm, humid conditions of tropical regions combined with socio economic factors such as poor sanitation and limited access to health care to create favorable environments for pathogen transmission and persistence. As a results in tropical diseases which often present with nonspecific febrile symptoms, leading to misdiagnosis and late treatment which can increase the morbidity and mortality (35). Machine learning algorithms that integrate clinical symptoms, laboratory findings and basic epidemiological data have shown promise in differentiating among confusable tropical diseases (43). For instance, models trained on combination of fevers characteristics, rash patterns, GI symptoms and hematological parameters can improve the distinction between malaria, dengue and other febrile illness. By helping the clinicians in real-time decision making, such symptoms based AI-tools can reduce the risk of misdiagnosis and helps in prioritize the appropriate treatment and therapies, especially in low-middle income countries (35).

4.4. Incorporation of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) for accurate determination

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) is an emerging subject in AI that seeks to make the AI models more transparent, interpretable and trustworthy for clinical users. In context of tropical disease diagnosis, the area where clinicians often lack access to sophisticated computational expertise, XAI can bridge the gap between black-box models and actionable clinical decisions. Greater multidisciplinary collaboration among diverse clinicians, data scientists and biomedical engineers is required to develop solid, domain specific XAI methods that align with clinical workflows (44). The efficiency of explainability is largely depended on how human users interpret the ML model outputs. Although explainable models may achieve comparable performance to non-explainable models, their utility in practice depends on factors such as the number and type of input variables, the structure of target class and the clarity of the explanation provided. As these factors may impact the performance of explainable ML and non-explainable ML models it makes the direct comparisons difficult. Nevertheless when combine with XAI it can enhance

clinicians confidence and also facilitate the model validation and support the regulatory approval, making the way for the safe and scalable deployment of AI-based diagnostic tools in NTDs settings (45).

5. AI in Public Health Surveillance & Epidemiology for NTDs

5.1. Artificial Intelligence enabled early warning for prevention of outbreak

Predictive modelling for disease epidemics for Neglected Tropical Diseases is another big area where Artificial Intelligence has proven useful. Predictive models are really important for figuring out the course of an outbreak finding risks and coming up with containment strategies (16). Artificial Intelligence powered predictive models use machine learning algorithms to look at the data on disease distribution demographics, environmental conditions and social behaviours to predict how an outbreak will unfold. These models help public health experts predict what is likely to happen identify people who're susceptible

to diseases in areas where the diseases are common and plan for the right remedies (46). Predictive modelling is a way to project the distribution of infectious disease epidemics. By looking at data and recognizing trends in how diseases spread Artificial Intelligence powered models can forecast future outbreaks of diseases like dengue, leishmaniasis and schistosomiasis. This allows health professionals to take steps to prevent outbreaks before they happen. Many Artificial Intelligence techniques, such, as machine learning, deep learning and reinforcement learning have been used to forecast the spread of Neglected Tropical Diseases. How well containment measures work. (47)

5.2. Models for predicting disease transmission dynamics and hotspot regions.

Models are designed to predict disease transmission dynamics and hotspot regions which came under into three main categories: compartmental mathematical models, spatial/statistical models, and machine learning/deep learning models.

Table 2: Epidemic Modeling Methods: Features and Applications

Feature	Compartmental Models	Spatial/Statistical Models	Machine Learning Models
Primary Output	Epidemic curves; R_0 estimates (49)	Hotspot maps; clustering zones (50)	Predicted case counts; outbreak probability (53)
Temporal Resolution	Continuous (ODEs) or discrete	Static or spatio-temporal (51)	High-frequency time-series (53)
Spatial Resolution	Often homogeneous (unless metapopulation) (49)	High (point-level to regional) (50)	Variable (depends on input data) (53)
Data Requirements	β , γ , population size (49)	Case locations; population at risk (51)	Large labeled datasets; diverse features(53)
Interpretability	High (mechanistic) (49)	Moderate (statistical) (51)	Low to moderate (black-box) (53)
Best For	Understanding transmission mechanisms; intervention evaluation (49)	Identifying high-risk geographic areas (50)	Early warning; multi-factor prediction (53)
Computational Cost	Low to moderate (49)	Moderate (Kriging/MCMC high) (51)	High (deep learning) (53)

As part of global health concerns, AI and ML systems are vital for avoiding and managing NTDs and tropical infectious diseases. AI/ML solutions are used rapidly as traditional epidemic models typically provide a limited view of the distribution of diseases and their causes. To make forecasts more accurate and track illnesses in time new methods use genomic data along with environmental and patient information (48). Modern methods now rely on data and environmental and patient information. This approach helps to improve forecast accuracy. Artificial intelligence models, like learning and advanced neural networks are used. These models have replaced the way of identifying pandemics, which relied on humans. Deep learning and neural networks are now used for identification. These models are more efficient, than human-driven tools. They make use of data, environmental data and patient data to forecast and track illnesses. Genomic data is used alongside patient information. The goal is to improve forecast accuracy and enable real-time illness surveillance. These models detect patterns, suggest potential future outbreaks, and drive the idea of public health actions (46).

5.3. Epidemic Forecasting and AI Integration:

Epidemic forecasting is a healthcare area that has substantially benefited from because of abundance of available data. Based on historical data, AI improves the prediction of disease occurrence and progression across health, social movement, environmental and disease history domains (53). For instance, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and graph-based algorithms assist AI in estimating the distribution of resources and NTD disease spread in endemic regions. These methods are really useful when it comes to giving advice on policies and things to do especially when it comes to new cases of diseases like tropical diseases that spread quickly. Similar to this we can use computers to look at sets of data that show where and when things happen which helps us keep a close eye on disease outbreaks in different areas and at different times (54).

5.3.2. Application of Machine Learning and Big Data in Disease Prediction:

Disease prediction and management have really improved because of data analytics and machine

learning. These technologies are very good at finding diseases on. They help doctors make decisions about what to do especially when it comes to neglected diseases. Data analysts and researchers use some techniques like forests support vector machines and deep neural networks to study complex data sets (55). They look closely at the data to find patterns and make predictions about when diseases will break out. Machine learning is a help to doctors and researchers when they have to make decisions, about patient care. Data analytics and machine learning make disease prediction and management better. These tools make it possible to detect diseases and manage them better, tropical and neglected diseases. Researchers use machine learning to analyze data. Find solutions to disease problems. Disease prediction and management are getting better all the time with data analytics and machine learning (56). Machine learning and data analytics play a role in disease management. They help doctors and researchers make decisions, about care. They do this to find patterns and relationships that we would not be able to see because these methods are more powerful, than the usual ways we use statistics. These techniques enables the prediction of various disease occurrences, their courses, and their prognoses using a variety of input sources, including wearable device data, genetics, and electronic medical records (57)

Numerous approaches to epidemic prediction models and their use in managing epidemics have been examined in various contexts:

- **Dengue fever prediction:** CNNs have been used to forecast the dengue fever epidemics in tropical regions using demographic and climate data. This strategy shows how AI models may effectively allocate limited healthcare resources and prevent NTD (58).
- **TB Relapse Prediction:** ML techniques using logistics regression and Random Forests have efficiently predicted TB relapse with low resource use. While TB isn't an NTD, this shows AI methodology that can be adapted for NTDs like Chagas disease and Human African Trypanosomiasis (59).

- COVID-19 Modelling (Proof-of-Concept):** Studies on COVID-19 using spatiotemporal models (GTNNWR) shows that basic SEIR models couldn't fit the real data as well as models which includes metrics like immunizations and social distancing. The winter death rate was reduced to 45%, which highlights the value of AI in pandemic management. These procedures are transferable to NTD outbreak management (58).

Table 3: Summary of AI and ML Studies in Infectious Disease Prediction and Modeling

SI No.	Study focus	Methodology/Technology used	Key Findings/Contributions	References
1.	AI and ML applications in infection prediction	AI, ML, DL, public health data, patient data	AI/ML improved disease prediction and public health interventions.	(60)
2.	AI-based CDSS for antimicrobial resistance prediction	ML with MALDI-TOF MS; Random Forest	High accuracy in predicting antibiotic resistance; Random Forest AUC 0.95.	(61)
3.	ML techniques for TB relapse prediction	Logistic regression, Random Forests, Boosting	Efficient prediction of TB relapse with less resource use.	(62)
4.	Role of AI in infectious disease modeling	SIR, SEIR, stochastic models, big data analytics	Enhanced predictive capacity for epidemics; ethical considerations highlighted.	(63)
5.	Real-time epidemic prediction using AI and cloud computing	Cloud computing, wearable device data, epidemiological models	Improved real-time outbreak Predictions and resource allocation.	(64)
6.	Spatial-temporal modeling of measles transmission	High-dimensional neural networks, TSIR model	SFNN outperformed TSIR in long-term forecasting; spatial hierarchies were observed.	(65)
7.	Climate-driven dynamics of marine pathogens	Genomic and environmental data integration	Revealed climate influence on Vibrio spread; predicted infections with high sensitivity.	(66)
8.	Dynamic COVID 19 transmission modeling in Medan, Indonesia	DEEPCOV, deep learning, transmission modeling	Enhanced forecasting and public health responses to COVID-19 in Medan.	(67)
9.	Early detection of COVID-19 via health tracker data	Reinforcement Learning, multi layer perceptron	Reduced data needs, improved early detection, balanced timeliness and accuracy.	(68)

6. Challenges in AI-Driven Drug Discovery, Diagnosis, Epidemiology for NTDs

Despite the substantial growth, the integration of AI into drug discovery, diagnosis and epidemiology of NTDs continues to face many scientific, infrastructural and practical challenges. Overcoming these limitations it is essential to ensure that AI-driven solutions are robust, generalizable and applicable in real world NTD-endemic settings.

6.1. Challenges in AI-Driven Drug Discovery for NTDs:

AI-based drug discovery depends on large, high quality and diverse datasets that are often limited or biased for NTDs. Generally most of the models are trained in high income country screening data and may not reflect the genetic and metabolic diversity of pathogens in low and middle income countries which leads to poor generalizability (16). DL models acts as “black box” systems, that makes it difficult to interpret the molecular features drive predictions and complicating their integration into classical drug development workflows (69). Alongside the regulatory frameworks and standardized benchmarks for NTDs specific AI platforms remain underdeveloped which delays the translation of AI-generated data into clinical candidates (16).

6.2. Challenges in AI-Assisted Diagnosis in NTDs

AI-driven diagnostic tools particularly in imaging, Smartphone-based based apps and tele-pathology are highly sensitive to quality of data and acquisition conditions. In NTD endemic regions datasets are often limited, fragmented and collected from very limited sites results in increasing the risk of algorithmic bias and poor performance in new populations. Computational hardware and reliable network connectivity in rural LMIC further restrict the deployment of AI system that required high resolution inputs, stable internet or cloud computing, so tools that are validated from urban countries may fail in remote clinics results in delayed diagnosis (70).

6.3. Challenges in AI-Driven Epidemiology and Surveillance

AI-driven epidemiological models generally depend on timely, accurate and spatially resolved data on disease incidence, prevalence and risk factors. Many NTDs where surveillance systems are weak or incomplete and reporting is often delayed, which decreases the predictive power of models. Geospatial and climate-linked models are prone to overfit to region specific, limiting their transferability across the regions with different socioeconomic profiles. Combining AI-driven outbreak forecasts into public health decision making remains limited by political, logistical and financial factors remains a big challenge in LMICs where preparedness capacity are already low (71).

6.4. Cross-Cutting Implementation Challenges

Many cross-cutting challenges affect AI across NTD related drug discovery, diagnosis and surveillance. It includes limited data and biasness mainly for under-represented endemic populations; that are limited to computational resources and high end infrastructure in LMICs; lack of interoperability between AI tools and existing electronic health records and lack of standardized evaluation metrics and benchmark datasets for NTD-specific tasks. Addressing these hurdles it will require strong collaboration between computational scientists, clinicians, public-health experts and policymakers as they need to design AI solutions which are not only accurate but also practical, interpretable and equitable for NTD affected countries (72).

7. Ethical Considerations in the Application of AI to Neglected Tropical Diseases

The application of artificial intelligence (AI) for the diagnosis and control of neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) raises important ethical concerns. Most NTDs affect the poor in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). As such, it is crucial to deal with these concerns seriously and systematically in order to harness AI for the good of reducing health inequities rather than worsening them (70).

7.1. Data Privacy and Confidentiality

The AI system performance heavily depends on the data quality and availability of the datasets which includes clinical records, images, genomic

information, and infectious disease surveillance information. Many of these data are sourced from unreserved communities in NTD-endemic countries where awareness on digital governance and their data rights are limited. There are thus concerns on issues of data confidentiality, informed consent and the risk of data misuse during data storage, processing and sharing (72). In many low and middle income countries, there is a lack of regulation on health data and protection of health information. With increased use of cloud storage and mobile health devices the risks for data protection breaches and compromise is greater than ever before. Therefore stronger anonymisation protocols, higher levels of data encryption and clearer ethics around informed consent are necessary for the deployment of ethical AI for health and patient benefit. Patients and communities should be aware of where their health information is coming from and what happens to it post collection. Ultimately sovereignty of data and security of information are critical to building and maintaining public trust in systems of health using AI (70).

7.2. Algorithmic Bias and Representativeness

Algorithmic bias is a significant ethical issue for the deployment of AI. Machine learning models are only as good as the data on which they have been trained, and if this data has been gathered within a geographic and demographic bubble or inconsistently, models are likely to perform differently for different populations (73). Models for NTDs are further complicated by strain of parasite, environment, and patient-specific factors. Current diagnostic systems based on images (e.g. computer-vision trained CNNs) have been validated on relatively small datasets in limited sites and there is real potential for these systems to be biased to particular endemic settings. In the neediest communities, this could result in inaccurate, delayed, or suboptimal diagnosis and treatment (74). There is a need for increased development and utilization of diverse, multi-regional datasets and robust external validation in addition to transparent reporting of performance by demographic subgroup. Fairness in AI requires continuous monitoring and re-tuning rather than assumption of universal applicability (73).

7.3. Infrastructure Gaps in Low-Resource Settings

Ethical concern that surrounds AI in NTD management are linked with healthcare infrastructure that are endemic regions. Many of the world's NTD-endemic countries have unstable power supplies and inadequate computer infrastructure for even the simplest of tasks, making it impossible to simply install new AI-based technologies without an appropriate hardware and internet backbone to support them. Excluding populations who could most benefit from advanced tools, in favour of those with the best connected hospitals and health systems would be a missed opportunity for improvement, and the tools must be designed with this constraint in mind (74). If AI systems are locked to use in well-equipped urban hospitals or research institutions, communities and populations in rural and remote locations will continue to be marginalized. Ethical use of AI requires context-aware design. AI systems and tools must be implemented in a form that is appropriate and usable in low resource settings and compatible with existing health infrastructure. Failing to do so could exacerbate health inequities rather than addressing them (70).

7.4. Equity and Accessibility

As AI is being explored as a potential approach to address the NTDs, an important ethical concern remains whether these innovations will actually reach the populations those are most affected by these diseases. Historically, much advancement in healthcare technologies and tools has failed to achieve meaningful improvements in low-resource settings, instead becoming concentrated within the high-income research institutions (17) For ethical AI to be practically implemented, it must be affordable, scalable and compatible with existing health infrastructure. Basic facilities at primary health care centers such as stable power supply, internet connectivity and computing power are often unavailable especially in endemic regions. Most current AI systems require expensive servers and computing power, making them difficult to scale up for large implementation in low- and middle- income countries. Developers and innovators need to develop systems keeping in mind the context specific limitations (70). Furthermore, the active involvement of local healthcare workers and policymakers into the design and implementation of these systems is

important to ensure the improving both functionality and appropriateness. Ethical innovation must be conceived through participatory processes, rather than through imposition of externally-generated solutions.

7.5. Transparency and Explainability

Although current deep learning models achieve high accuracy rates, they are often explained poorly, making them so called “black-box” models. In clinical practice, transparency is critical and a lack thereof can hinder the adoption of such systems by clinicians and even obstruct the approval process by regulators. As AI is increasingly, it contributes to diagnosis or treatment decisions, it becomes an ethically highly important area where understanding the system’s reasoning behind the system’s decision is essential (70). Interpretable results and traceable decisions are key aspects of Explainable AI to ensure accountability. Clinicians should remain in control of the outputs and make appropriate decisions utilising their expertise and professional judgment. Transparency is key to gaining trust and to getting models accepted within clinical environments and ensures responsible use (74).

7.6. Accountability and Governance

As AI is rolled out for NTD management, questions will raise to accountability in the event of an error or bad outcome. Effective governance will be needed to define the standards for validating these tools, how they will be monitored, and how they will be regulated. The adoption of ethical AI should extend beyond technical evaluation and require policy guidance from regulatory bodies. Regulatory authorities, such as government health organizations, should develop disease-specific guidelines and regulatory frameworks on the safe, reliable, and equitable use of AI for infectious disease diagnosis and treatment (74).

8. CONCLUSION & FUTURE PERSPECTIVES:

The implementation of AI into the management of NTDs demonstrates a major advancement in the global health care. AI has represented significant potential in improving early diagnosis, fast drug discovery, enhancing disease surveillance and also support the clinical decision making, especially in

regions where the healthcare resources is limited. By converting large and complex datasets into meaningful insights, AI can be useful to overcome several challenges related to control and treatment of NTDs. Despite its advantages, the implementation of AI in the management of NTD is associated with important ethical, infrastructural and regulatory concerns. Problems related to data privacy, algorithmic bias, transparency and governance must be addressed carefully to make sure that AI technology should improve the healthcare outcomes for low income populations rather than the increasing existing healthcare inequalities. Thus, AI systems should be developed as affordable, context-specific and resource-efficient those are suitable for low-resource healthcare which will be important for their successful implementation. Future of NTD progress depends on strong association among the clinicians, researchers, policymakers, technologists and local communities. Increased focus on explainable AI, participatory approaches and equitable healthcare policies can enhance the trust and support the long-term sustainability of AI-based interventions. With appropriate implementation strategies and strong ethical governance, AI has the potential role in reducing the burden of NTDs and contribute to a more inclusive, sustainable and reliable global healthcare system. Moreover association of AI with mobile health technologies, telemedicine and wearable diagnostic tools can further enhance the NTD management at the community level. Continuous monitoring and predictive analytics can help in the early detection of outbreak in the prone regions which are at higher risk, which enables the quicker health responses and makes distribution of healthcare resources more efficiently.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I acknowledge to the Department of Pharmaceutics, Nemcare group of Institution.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Debajit Dutta and Monideepa Dey contributed to the conceptualization of the review, literature search, data

collection, manuscript writing and critical revision of the review manuscript. Gyandeeep Bhattacharyya, Partha Pratim Saikia contributed to literature search, data collection and manuscript writing. Minerva Kalita, Khyati Mishra were responsible for the preparation of tables and figures. Juti Rani Devi, Bhargab Jyoti Sahariah supervised the manuscript.

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HOW TO CITE: Debajit Dutta, Monideepa Dey, Gyandeeep Bhattacharyya, Partha Pratim Saikia, Minerva Kalita, Khyati Mishra, Juti Rani Devi*, Bhargab Jyoti Sahariah, Artificial Intelligence for Neglected Tropical Diseases: Enhancing Diagnosis, Drug Discovery and Public Health Surveillance, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (6), 1123-1141. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21019227>

